

OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES TO SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES: A STUDY OF SILLANWALI WOODEN HANDICRAFTS

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ABSTRACT: *The purpose of the current study is to investigate the effect of business constraints on firm's performance and growth potential of SMEs. The study also evaluates the role of firm level characteristics in accessing the finance. The study utilizes the primary data collected through detailed survey of wooden handicraft SMEs of Sillanwali, a tehsil of district Sargodha, Punjab. The handicraft articles of Sillanwali are well known throughout Pakistan and across the world due to its fascinated and attractive designs. The study surveyed 120 firms by a well-structured questionnaire. The business constraints include of Accessing of finance, Cost of financing, Tax rates, Tax Administration, Price instability and Inflation, Political instability, Un-affordability of CNC machines, Severe competition and Inefficient cost of electricity. The study utilizes the ordinary least squares method and logistic regression method for estimating the models.*

The study estimates the probability of accessing the finance by SMEs through considering the variables of firm level Characteristics i.e. firm size, firm age, sales, capital and collateral. The performance of firms are checked by considering the effect of nine business constraints i.e. access of finance, cost of financing, tax rates, tax administrations, inflation and price instability, political instability, un-affordability of CNC machines, inefficient cost of electricity and severe competitions on sales of firms per month. Similarly, the income growth potential of SMEs is estimated by checking the effect of six business constraints i.e. political instability, shortage of electricity, accessing of finance, limited access to new markets, lack of government subsidies and firm innovation on sales of firms during previous five years.

The results show that the variables of Firm size, Firm age, Capital, Sales and Collateral have positive effect on increasing the probability of firm to access the finance. The performance of firm is negatively affected by business constraints. The probability of growth potential of Sillanwali SMEs is also negatively affected by business constraints. It suggested that any unit increase in the index value of business constraints will result to reduce the probability of income growth potential by their respective values.

KEYWORDS: *SMEs; Handicrafts; Growth Potential; Performance*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

SMEs have a pivotal role in driving the forces of economic growth. These forces help to attain industrial growth and development of SME sector (Eigbiremolen & Igberaese, 2013). This is due to SMEs great potential in ensuring diversification of industrial production. SMEs contribute in economic growth by utilization of local raw materials, mobilization of idle resources, specialization in manufacturing products and creation of employment for labor force (Rasak, 2012). They play critical role to alleviate poverty by job creation and responsible to improve socio-economic development of a country (Akingunola, 2011). In order to improve socio economic conditions, SMEs assist to empower industrial growth and social welfare of the people. Investment is important for uplifting the SME sector of any country. Governments play a vital role by checking the performance of SMEs in order to ensure ample investment in small businesses. The private investment is also important to industrial growth as it leads to improve performance of SMEs by makes investment to small businesses and strengthens the domestic markets.

The economy of world comprises of developed and developing countries. It is worthily accepted that SMEs make a significant contribution to political infrastructure and socio-economic conditions of countries (Matlay & Westhead, 2005). Moreover, a growing SME sector is considered to be important

for sustainable economic development and helps to provide a competitive advantage in production at local, regional and national levels (Porter, Lopez-Claros, Schwab, & Sala-I-Martin, 2006). In developed countries, the operations of SMEs are flexible due to inherited advantage of size, service and knowledge based innovation (S. Khan, 2015). Moreover, SMEs respond rapidly to new opportunities and contribute to create jobs for idle labor force. Therefore, the share of SMEs to GDP of developed countries is higher than developing countries.

Developing countries are characterized as low income countries due to factors responsible to failure of SMEs. These factors include inaccessibility of finance, inadequate infrastructure, high tax invasion and poor economic conditions. Furthermore, these problems create uncertainty regarding investment in small businesses and result to decline SMEs share in GDP of developing countries. Figure 1 shows contribution of SMEs to GDP of developed and developing countries.

Figure 1 Percentage of SMEs contributions in GDP

Source: SMEDA, US Commission Report (2010), Statistics on SME sector in India

The figure shows SMEs contribution to GDP of developed (Japan, USA, UK) and developing (Malaysia, India, Pakistan, Indonesia) countries. Among developed countries, SMEs in Japan contribute 55.3% to GDP followed by 52% and 51% in USA and UK. Similarly, among developing countries, SMEs in Malaysia contribute 32% to GDP of country followed by 31%, 30% and 6% in India, Pakistan and Indonesia.

According to (Westhead & Wright, 2000), absence of adequate finance for growth of small businesses is a common problem to develop and developing countries. In the industrially developed and developing economies, a large number of growing SMEs need access to wide range of sources of finance. SMEs in these economies rely on long term funding from banks, commercial institutions and government organizations (Manigart et al., 2000). But, when firms expenditures exceed the availability of financial resources, they have to rely on external sources of finance i.e. loans from non-governmental organizations. The availability of finance from external sources is restrictive due to terms and conditions attach with loan process which affect the business growth of SMEs (Hussain, Millman, & Matlay, 2006). So, in developed countries, the economic policies and knowledge based experience provide a foundation to proper utilization of resources with the help of effective management system. The figure 2 represents some basic differences in developing and developed countries regarding SMEs.

Figure 2 Difference between developing and developed countries regarding SMEs

Source: SMEDA, US Commission Report (2010), Statistics on SME sector in India

1.2 Profile of SMEs in Pakistan

Pakistan is an SME economy that has 30% SMEs contribution to GDP (J. Qureshi & Herani, 2011). The economic growth of any country depends upon the investment and SMEs are the main sector that is important to make investment. The purpose of SMEs is to utilize local raw material such as labor, skills and expertise in order to channelize them in a productive way. This process of investment helps to increase the production and improving the varieties of local products that attract the customers from across the world. Innovative products can be manufactured by introducing technological advancement in production process of SMEs. The innovation in product motivates further SMEs to take step in local industry by grounding new setup or investing in already operating SMEs. The increase in production due to better technology increases the exports that lead to increase employment and income of a country. In this way, SMEs directly contribute to economic growth of a country.

The economy of Pakistan heavily relies on SME sector for jobs, revenue by exporting, foreign investments, industrial production and skills development (Kongolo, 2010). SMEs are important for economy of Pakistan as they are considered backbone to economic development and enhance socio-economic conditions of country (M. M. Khan, 2015). In Pakistan, government and State Bank of Pakistan try to develop SME sector by providing assistance regarding finance availability but still there is difficulty in achieving optimal productivity from this sector (Jasra, Hunjra, Rehman, Azam, & Khan, 2011).

Despite of all significant efforts made by government and stakeholders, this sector is facing many challenges including of regulatory requirement difficulties, inappropriate tax rates, inadequate infrastructure, price instability, small scope of business, non-competitive products at international level and most important difficulty in accessing the finance (Bari & Cheema, 2005; Jasra et al., 2011; S. Khan, 2015; Ul Hassan, 2008). In order to tackling these challenges and developing the SME sector by providing finance/technical assistance, some institutions have been established by government (Jasra

et al., 2011). For example, in 1998 government established an institution named “Small and Medium Enterprises Development Authority (SMEDA)” to improve the growth of SMEs in Pakistan. SMEs Banks were established for filling the gap of shortage of finance. SME Business Support Fund (BSF) was established to assist both SMEs and Business Development Services Providers (BDSPs). The BDSPs are institutions which give assistance to SMEs by giving loans after getting grants from government. The non-government organization named “Aik Hunr, Aik Nagar (AHAN)” was established to cover the broad service portfolio and cluster skill development through training. Among these institutions, SMEDA is responsible for designing SME policy by addressing the core issues face by SME sector of Pakistan (S. Khan, 2015).

Similarly, the government has deficiency in promotion of export liberalization policies and barrier free trade to extend exports across boarder. The business growth of SMEs highly depends upon exports and Pakistan’s SME sector only contributes 25% to exports of manufactured goods (SMEDA). It is duty of government to take measures for sustainable development of SMEs by providing assistance and monitoring regarding these challenges.

Government support and investment are important instruments for creating opportunities regarding growth potential of SMEs in Pakistan. In Pakistan, small SMEs are classified according to employee’s size and majority of SMEs have employees not more than 10. Moreover, majority of small SMEs are operating at rural sector that provide a great source of job opportunities to local labor force (SMEDA Survey Report, 2009).

Figure 3 shows contribution of SMEs in economy of Pakistan. The contribution of SMEs to GDP is 30% followed by 25% exports of manufactured commodities. Similarly, SME sector provides 70% employment to non-agriculture work force followed by 35% value addition in manufacturing output.

Figure 3 SMEs contribution in economy of Pakistan

Source: SMEDA, SBP (2013)

Followed the report by (SMEDA Survey Report, 2009), SMEs in Pakistan are also distributed according to status of ownership. The status of ownership is classified under the heads of sole proprietorship, registered partnership and society base ownership. In Pakistan, about 74% of SMEs are sole proprietor followed by 13% registered partnership and only 2% SMEs are operating at society’s ownership. Figure 4 shows status of ownership regarding SMEs of Pakistan.

In all over the world, SMEs are defined on three bases i.e. volume of sales, assets of firms and paid up capital. According to European commission, an SME is a firm having number of employees up to 250.

Figure 4 SMEs distribution according to ownership of business

Source: (SMEDA Survey Report, 2009)

Similarly in Pakistan, there are different institutions who define SMEs according to employment size, annual sale and fixed assets. Table 1 shows definition of SMEs according to institutions of Pakistan.

Table 1 SME definitions according to different institutions in Pakistan

Institution	Employment size	Annual sale	Fixed assets
State Bank of Pakistan (SBP)	Not over 250	Up to 300 Million	RS 100 Million
Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (PBS)	Not less than 10	N/A	N/A
SMEDA	up to 250	up to RS 250 Million	N/A
SME Bank	Not over 250	N/A	RS 100 Million

Source: Small and Medium Enterprises Development Authority (SMEDA)

Further, SMEs can be classified as micro, small and medium enterprises. SMEs are defined as micro enterprises having number of employees 1 to 9. SMEs are defined as small enterprises having number of employees 10 to 49. Similarly, medium enterprises are those firms having number of employees 50 to 250 (Dar, Ahmed, & Raziq, 2017).

In Pakistan, 99% of industrial sector is comprises of SMEs and they play a leading role to growth of firms. Pakistan is an SME economy and there are different SMEs clusters which are producing variety of products. For example, Sialkot SMEs are famous for production of sport products, SMEs of Sargodha region are famous for producing electric fitting accessories, wool work and wooden handicrafts, Faisalabad SMEs are famous for producing garments and clothes whereas Gujranwala SMEs are famous for producing utensils.

Among SMEs of Pakistan, wooden handicrafts are important SMEs to provide employment for large number of labor force. The SMEs of wooden handicrafts utilize local artists and resources at its optimal level. The manufactured products are exported to international markets and provide a great source of revenue to economy. Due to trade barriers and irrational behavior by government of Pakistan, the exports volume of wooden handicrafts are less than its competing countries. The current study attempted to check the growth potential and performance regarding SMEs of Sillanwali wooden handicrafts. The products of Sillanwali handicrafts are famous for producing variety of fascinated geometrically designs base wooden items.

Figure 5 Decline in exports of wood products in Pakistan

Source: WITS (World Integrated Trade Solution)

According to facts and figures provided by “World Integrated Trade Solution (WITS)”, the export volume of wood made articles is at diminishing trend. Figure 5 explains the trends regarding exports of wooden articles of Pakistan. In 2013, the export volume of wooden articles was thousands US\$ 52,682 that reduce to thousands US\$ 38,964 in 2017.

1.3 SMEs of Sillanwali

Sillanwali is a fertile area having geographic coordinates of 31°49'45N to 72°32'22E. Sillanwali is famous for its SMEs that are operating at local level and responsible of providing employment to majority of people. The SMEs in Sillanwali comprise of handicraft manufacturing firms and wood carving units. The handicraft products which are designing and manufacturing at Sillanwali SMEs have great potential to capture the attention of international buyers and helps to increase the industrial growth and exports of country.

1.4 Objectives

The objectives of the study are:

- To identify the firm-level characteristics which increase the chances of access to finance.
- To investigate the effect of business constraints on performance of SMEs in Sillanwali.
- To investigate the effect of business constraints on growth potential of SMEs in Sillanwali.
- To explore the potential export markets for Sillanwali handicrafts.
- To suggest some policy recommendations based upon study findings.

1.5 Significance of the study

The main focus of the study is upon SMEs of Sillanwali, a tehsil of district Sargodha which is well known in throughout Pakistan and at international level for its best geometric and oriented handicraft designs. Wooden handicrafts as major occupation contribute 70-75% in local employment. The purpose of current study is to explore this industry by indicating the major business constraints that badly affect the business growth of SMEs. Moreover, provide a comprehensively information about all aspects cover by this industry.

1.6 Statement of problem

SME sector is a backbone for economy of Pakistan. But, due to irrational policies by government and improper information regarding SMEs of Pakistan, this sector is facing number of challenges i.e. failure of financial system, hurdles in administrative process, high costs of electricity and high tax rates etc. These challenges directly affect the growth of small business that leads to deficiency in production. SMEs of Sillanwali are among those SMEs that are not paying proper attention by government in order to address these key challenges. So, the current study identifies the performance and income growth situation of Sillanwali SMEs by incorporating the business constraints. No study, has yet utilized quantitative analysis in identifying major business constraints and their effect on business growth of Sillanwali SMEs in order to check performance and income growth potential by firms. This analysis gives impetus to address the key business constraints by confronting the framework that integrates all barriers and constraints faced by Sillanwali SMEs.

1.7 Plan of the study

The rest of paper is classified as; section 2 discusses about literature review by arranging contents according to objectives of study. Section 3 describes about methodology and estimation models. Results and discussions are described in section 4 while section 5 refers to conclusion and policy recommendations.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This section describes the reviewing of research articles relating to SMEs of Pakistan and the world. The literature review is classified according to review regarding accessing of finance, business constraints, innovation in SMEs and exports of products manufactured by SMEs. Section 2.2 describes the literature review regarding accessibility of finance. Section 2.3 describes the review regarding business constraints that are facing by SME sector. Section 2.4 describes the review of research articles regarding innovation behavior in SMEs. Section 2.5 describes the review regarding problems in exports by SMEs. Section 2.6 and 2.7 describes the review of research articles regarding SMEs of Pakistan and SMEs in Sillanwali respectively.

2.1 International literature review of SMEs regarding finance constraints

Different studies have been conducted to point out sources of finance required to improve capital gain and income generation of economy through the provision of finance. Finance is to be considered a major constraint involve in hindrance the growth of SMEs. SMEs directly and indirectly contribute 90 to 99 % in corporate sector of economy. The hindrance in accessing the finance by SMEs involves of deficiency in provision the collateral requirements, inability of firm to achieve high profits and capital generate incapacity. Studies have found the three basic types of finance that can be access by a SME. Finance is obtained through formal sources, informal sources and source of Debt equity financing. In developed countries formal source is consider important while informal source is important in underdeveloped countries. In Europe about 99.5% of SMEs are involved in 55% gross production of corporate sector through formal source of finance (Daskalakis, Jarvis, & Schizas, 2013; S. Khan, 2015; Ul Hassan, 2008). Banks are considered as main instrument to provide short term and long term loans. Egyptian economy case is important to note as establishing of stock exchange formal finance source with SMEs. The purpose of stock exchange was to uplift the finance base of SMEs to increase capital and boost the economy to employment generation. In case of Zimbabwe, a study evaluates the barriers faced by SMEs to access the finance from banks. The study provides some sort of solutions to motivate the SMEs for further improvement. The studies highlight that the alliances between Banks and SMEs provide a strategic partnership to alleviate the problems regarding finance and improve the SMEs accessibility towards finance (Matamanda & Chidoko, 2017; Maunganidze, 2013; Ul Hassan, 2008).

Small and medium enterprises operate under the problems of financing constraints and determinants of economy to determine the growth of any country. Different studies evaluate the SMEs growth and their effect on economy. The determinants are also highlighted that access by SMEs to effect the growth of economy. In the case of Nigeria, the study conducted to check the relationship between growth of SMEs and development of economy. The study highlighted the casual relationship between them. Results show the development of economy depends upon SMEs growth as it is main source to income generation for a country. The study also evaluates Uni-directional causality running between them. The finance is considered a major constraint to growth of economy. The proper management by government, provision of infrastructure and finance availability to SMEs is necessary for growth perspective of economy. Loans to SMEs, Interest rate and inflation are responsible to effect the GDP growth of economy (Eigbiremolen & Igberaese, 2013).

Similarly the determinants of financial resources, Marketing Strategy, Technological resources, Information Access, Government Support, Business Plan and Entrepreneur Skill are considered the major factors to effect the growth of economy (Jasra et al., 2011).

SMEs are operating across the world and their functioning is according to rules of that country. SMEs are system of jobs creation and it associate with some factors. In the case study of Jordan conducted by Jordanian Young Economists Society (JYES), jobs creation ability and its associate issue are described in context of SMEs. The study highlights the importance of SMEs in the economy of Jordan. In Jordan, about 98.5% of registered firms are SMEs that contribute to 50% in GDP and 60% in formal jobs creation. According to study results, it is interpreted that in startup firms and firms functioning less than 5 years of age have high ability of job creation. The study also attempt to denote issues and problems internally, externally faced by SMEs in Jordan. The issues comprise of limited internal resources, cost of doing business, government irregularities, accessing of finance, demand uncertainty and lack of credibility and reputation (Al-Mahrouq, 2010).

The factors involve in accessing the finance is described by (Abor & Quartey, 2010) by applying pooled order logit model in case of West African sub-region. The study is attempt to check whether there is similarities/dissimilarities in access of finance by west Africa sub-region as compare to other countries of SSA. By taking the World Bank's enterprise survey data, the study efforts to strongly check effects of firm characteristics i.e.; firm size, ownership, strength of legal rights and depth of credit information on access to finance.

A study was conducted to notice objective and subjective measures of accessing the finance to check the robustness. The study focused on (Modimootsile, 2005) interpretation that checks the problems attach with access of finance is through directly survey of issues regarding financing constraints. The study identify lack of collateral, inadequate credit history, high risk premiums, difficulties in providing credit worthiness, small cash flows, underdeveloped bank borrow, bank-borrower relationships and high transaction costs as major constraints to accessing finance in sub-region (Abor & Quartey, 2010).

Many studies have been identifying the financial practices and SMEs preference to access the financial sources. The aims of studies are threefold; firstly how SMEs access to financial sources? Secondary what are their preferences? Thirdly which are obstacles SMEs face in attaining these sources. The studies explore three types of financial sources naming as equity financing, debt financing and grant financing. Moreover, some studies identify personal income, loans from banks and grants from government and foreign NGOS (Akingunola, 2011; Alper & Hommes, 2013; Daskalakis et al., 2013; Hussain et al., 2006).

2.2 SMEs and business constraints

Different studies unleash these issues and describe some policy recommendations regarding enhancement of SMEs. political instability, finance accessing, technology level, innovation,

infrastructure, inefficient cost of finance, political hindrance, government policies ineffectiveness are some common issues identify by studies (Dar et al., 2017; Khalique, Isa, & Nassir Shaari, 2011).

(Khalique et al., 2011) also unleashes the SMEs functioning in knowledge base system and production base system. According to study, the traditional SMEs operate under the scheme of production function include of land, labor, capital. In the 21 century, the trend has been changed from production base economy to knowledge base economy. Knowledge based economy consist of intellectual factors and intellectual capital. The innovation, publicity, advancements are the same factors come under the definition of intellectual capital. The knowledge is major factor operate at knowledge base economy. The entrepreneur of SME better in management and has knowledge of market is better to survive in competitive markets of world. The issues and problems faced by SMEs operate in knowledge base economy at globalized markets are also highlighted by different studies. The most common issues are recession, low productivity, lacking in managerial capabilities, regularly burden, and barrier from sourcing and insufficient availability of finance (Al-Mahrouq, 2010; J. Qureshi & Herani, 2011; Saleh & Ndubisi, 2006).

Some studies identify the problems in middle handicraft sector and in exports hurdles. The main findings of the studies are the problems associated with handicrafts items' exporting. high cost of raw materials, lack of access to export credit, policy uncertainty labor regulation, lack of access to export credit, low subsidy, income tax, high excise, air freight problems, local transportations are major problems identify by these studies. Marketing Campaigns, promotions, positioning in Target Markets, Inform foreign purchasers, Alliance for technological marketing and financial strength, Sufficient Raw Materials at rational Prices, Active participation in International funfairs are some suggested policies (Ghouse, 2012; Ramlee & Berma, 2013).

Many studies explore the major obstacles faced by SMEs. Findings suggest two types of barriers, internal and external. The shortcomings/problems include finance accessing problems, technological innovation biases, absence of an effective business information infrastructure, energy crises, lack of strategic planning, unskilled human resources and poor landing strategies by banks (Bari & Cheema, 2005; Khawaja, 2006; RAZIQ, 2014; Zafar & Mustafa, 2017).

2.3 Literature review regarding Innovation in SMEs

Innovation as an integrated part of products design by SMEs is very important from the perspective of competition. In global market, the exports are totally relying on products uniqueness and ability to capture the attention of customers. The case study regarding the SMEs of Malaysia has been studied to focus the attention towards sources of products available for SMEs. The sources are classified as tangible and intangible in nature. The study shifted attention toward intangible resources as it is perceived to be most important for sustainable production. The intangible resources in production of products are rare and not easily be intimate, which ultimately create unique products of innovation not easily to compete by others SMEs products. The study research completely depends upon innovation development theory provided by Schumpeter 1934 who describe innovation as the future standards of performance used by decision makers in the economic system. The theory base on innovation and intangible resources namely Resource Based View (RBV) is also attributed in the study. This theory highlights the firm is a collection of unique resources of competitive advantage and all these resources don't possess potential to provide firm with sustained competitive advantage.

In context of RBV Greene et al. 1997 identify fives types of resources in RBV namely as human, social, physical, organizational and financial resources. Recently literature suggests six categories namely as physical, organizational, financial, reputational, human/intellectual and technological. Tangible resources are including of physical capital and assets of SMEs while intangible resources are human

skills, reputation, knowledge and human capital. The study also attribute with use of product innovation performance (PIP). The study identify that reputational resources have highest impact on product innovation performance as compared to other factors. The PIP is measured at 5 Linkert scale. The firm's performance depends upon intangible resources and reputational resource is major contributor to SMEs development and PIP analysis (Bakar & Ahmad, 2010).

Firms are competing at international level on the basis of brand oriented scheme. The firms can only compete by including the innovation item in their production. The innovation in product is necessary factor of achieving profit base status in market. A firm has capabilities to improve and introduce innovation in products. These capabilities categorize in business networks, knowledge acquisition and strategic management. Value chain is introduced in studies through innovation conceptual model. Business network are important in its effect of finding out solution regarding any business issue in product development domain. Knowledge acquisition domain introduces the new knowledge and resource commitment to exploit new markets for products. Strategic orientation linked the resources available to firm. All these three capabilities affect by the orientation of EO (Entrepreneurial Orientation), MO (Market Orientation), LO (Learning Orientation) and TO (Technological Orientation). The study has been conducted about these capabilities and orientations by taking three cases regarding producer, distributor and retailer. The research is qualitative in nature and concludes that innovation is not always necessary to achieve firm goal of achieving high profit in brand oriented markets. The acquisition of knowledge, production cost, resource and innovation in firms' production also taken as important factor to compete at international level of innovative items. A study has also been conducted in the same scenario to consider innovation as important factor embedded in competitive environment. The innovation is embedded in the orientations of process management, product, services and organizational structures. The empirical study has investigated a relationship between process, product, organizational and marketing with SMEs innovative, operational and financial. Firm innovation has positive and strongly impact of orientations of firms. Innovation of firm has not positively associate with financial activities and marketing perspective (Kim-Soon, Ahmad, Kiat, & Sapry, 2017; Serra & García, 2013).

In the case study conducted about small SMEs operate in Malaysia describe the patterns of innovation in production. The study conducted in-depth interview of eight SMEs owners and divide them in two groups. First group consist of ordinary owners of SMEs and other group include of owners whose background is poor in nature. The study also differentiates innovation patterns between small SMEs and large SMEs. The firm applies Greiner growth model and readiness theory. The Greiner growth model describes the innovation of firm as an important instrument at competitive atmosphere and ability to produce such products of innovation unique in every perspective. Readiness theory explains the concentration of innovation types in small firms. The findings suggests that incremental, administrative and product innovation are attribute to small SMEs. The SMEs have poor owner or which are small in scale survive on extensive nature to provide innovation at high cost (Ishak & Omar, 2013).

Different studies have been conducted on the innovation part of handicrafts in the world. The empirical study in the case of Fiji and Tonga is conducted to identify the determinants of innovation under the tourism perspective. The face to face interview of 368 interviews is conducted in Fiji and Tonga. The study identify eight determinants of innovation namely; products value added, design uniqueness, new product development, cultural uniqueness, advancement in technology, experience of owner to operate, ability to accept new trends and quality of raw materials.

The definition of innovation in handicraft industry as determinants of mention factors are conducted

by study under the base research provide by (Romijn & Albaladejo, 2002) and (Bhattacharya & Bloch, 2004). The logit model is used to check the effects of determinants on innovation variable while the robustness is check through probit model. The empirical findings suggest significant effect of determinants on innovation factor in the industry of Fiji and Tonga.

2.4 Literature review of SMEs regarding exports

Exports are important in context of world trade. Exports are the main engine of economic growth and development as it is main source of foreign earning for any country. Exports are unique in its nature as its characteristics depend upon the rules and regulations of native land. The developing or transition economies are struggling for their survivor in every field of economy. The main reason in their backwardness is consist of factors that hindrance its production side. Because it has been assume from very far time that production is necessary for exports. The exports are only performing if a country is efficient in producing products of unique quality after fulfilling their local needs. Exports depend upon the products which are able to compete in international markets. Pakistan is a developing country and it has also facing issues and problems regarding exports. The entrepreneur of Pakistan is lagging behind in increasing their exports.

For increase in imports, it is required to improve the SMEs production. In Pakistan as SMEs are 90 % portion of corporate sector, it is necessary to uplift SMEs side. The SMEs are responsible to produce those products of quality require to compete at international level.

According to (Köksal & Kettaneh, 2011), the exports are expensive at their startup and the firms are neglected in exporting due to high cost of managing. After a specific period, the exports achieve managerial effects by improving the quantity of exports. It provides strategic advantages and profit making ability to firm management. In corporate sector of economy, large firms can exports their products but SMEs always face issues and problems in its exporting. The SMEs have to face export barriers due to government inefficient policies, lack in innovative factor, rivalry at international market and especially the price adjustment process of products.

In any SMEs operating in economy of knowledge based, two types of factors involve in exporting barriers naming as internal and external barriers. The internal barriers are totally in control of firm and country but external factors are not controllable by country. The nature of internal barriers include of three issues; Informational, functional and marketing. External barriers include of procedural, governmental and environmental. In developed countries the external barriers are more problematic then internal because these countries are sufficient in their function. Internal barriers are dominated in transition economies (Köksal & Kettaneh, 2011).

The study conducted by (Khattak, Arslan, & Umair, 2011) explores the barriers face by SMES in exports and also highlight their effects on SMEs growth. The sample consists of 25 textile industries with a structural questionnaire and interview method. The study identify that internal barriers comprise of 68% and external barriers are 32% to be face by industries. The study highlights the percentage of internal barriers as Functional barriers 29%, Energy crises 39%, Environmental barriers 19% and marketing barriers 13%. While, the percentage of external barriers are as competitive barriers 45%, Environmental barriers 22% and procedural barriers 33%. Pakistan has competition with other SAARC countries in its exports.

The most important rival of Pakistan in exports is India. If we make comparison between the handicraft sectors of both countries, then India has much potential in exports of handicrafts as compare to Pakistan. But both of these countries are much behind then other SAARC countries in its exports. The reason involve is consist of transition or developing factor of both countries. These countries are still efforts to access new horizon of exports. Like Pakistan, India has also facing exports barriers and both

countries experience same factors of hindrance. The factors of licensing problems, no demand, high cost of raw materials, lack of access to raw materials, obsolete tools and equipment's, lack of access to export credit, high cost of credit, scarcity of skilled labor, labor regulations, high excise, poor infrastructure, policy uncertainty, local transportation, shipping problems, air freight problems, duty draw back reimbursement, low subsidy, income tax, internet connectivity, market awareness are the cause of export barriers of handicrafts in the case of India (Ghouse, 2012).

2.5 Literature review of SMEs regarding Pakistan

In context of Pakistan, the problems and constraints due to financing issues is highlighted by the studies. The case of Karachi; a city of Pakistan study the problems faced by SMEs operate in Karachi by formal and informal means of interview. The sample size include of 500 respondents SMEs conducted through convenient sample techniques. The predictors include of financing constraints, functional/internal barriers, government support by provision of incentives, and SMEs growth regress on SMEs financing.

The loans of short term with soft interest rate policies are also unavailable to SMEs (J. A. Qureshi, 2012). The studies are qualitative and quantitative in nature to describe the concept base and empirical base constraints ratio to SMEs growth. The conceptual framework of access possibilities frontier identify the transaction cost and information asymmetrical as a major financial constraint and other institutional instruments pitfalls. The transaction cost include of fixed cost describe the constraint behavior of finance which have to be bear by borrower in repayment of amount include of interest rate. The fixed transaction cost creates a wedge between the financial institutions and other the amount payable by borrower.

The interest rates are major factor to hindrance in accessing the formal source of finance (Beck, 2007). The financial institutions try to set the interest rate lower then clearing market rate as the higher interest rate reduce the repayment ratio of loan (Williamson, 1987). Moreover, the studies highlight the lenders borrowers' relationship a major bridge to advocacy of finance. The countries having developing nature are more involve in facing financing constraints. Whereas, the firms operate in developed countries has strong empirical evidence of institutional development to loans accessibility (Beck & Demirguc-Kunt, 2006). The "selection model of financial source" identifies the sources other than bank to reduce the dependability on finance from banks. The model allows the management of SMEs to adopt knowledge and other institutions as a framework to workout at need of finance (Giacosa & Mazzoleni, 2016).

The study regarding Pakistan conducted to highlight the sources of finance available to SMEs sector. The study explained the sources along with issues involve in hindrance the growth of SMEs. In Pakistan, there are 3.2 million businesses out of which there are 3 million SMEs. The SMEs comprise of 90% business stakes and 30% to GDP of country. The contribution in country's earnings is 25% and 70% population directly or indirectly involve in SMEs for livelihood (IFC 2012). Formal and informal sources are include of SME bank, Commercial banks, State bank of Pakistan, SMEDA, Trade development authority of Pakistan (TDAP), International financial agencies, Family, relatives, shopkeepers and landlords.

According to estimation by (Ul Hassan, 2008) 61 % informal finance is obtain through family and relatives, 30% through landlords and remaining is provided through shopkeepers. Improper infrastructure, Regulatory requirements difficulties, Shortage of skilled HR, Noncompetitive products, Lack of entrepreneurial expertise, Shortage/irregular availability of financing facilities, Inability to meet financing formalities/credit conditions, Lengthy documentation procedure, Small scope of business and Risk of default are major problems attribute to SMEs sector in Pakistan. It is necessary to make provision of infrastructure and especially the finance as it is major problem of SMEs (S. Khan, 2015).

Similarly, a study has been conducted in the case of Pakistan to evaluate the impact of financial sources on growth of SMEs by panel data analysis. The survey data of 78 SMEs for the three consecutive years of 2003, 2007 and 2010 has been analyzed. According to study the effect of internal funds, banks, family and friends, NBFC, on credit and other informal sources are regress on log of annual sales in order to highlight their effects on SMEs growth. The formal sources of finance have positive trending from year 2003 to 2010 and they positively affect the growth of firms. The informal sources have negatively effect in year 2003 and 2007 while the impact is dissipating in year 2010 (S. Khan, 2015).

The studies have been conducted regarding a specific SME operate in cities of Pakistan. The case study of electric fitting accessories in Sargodha, a city of Punjab, Pakistan is carried out by. The SME of electric accessories is operating from the very beginning but the products are of substandard and consume at local level. The study focused on the factor of importing China electrical accessories, which effect the local production and income generation capacity. The study tries to explain the efforts and role of local producers to compete with standards of china products to increase their sales. The data sets of 232 firms are used to evaluate qualitative analysis. The study estimated the models describing the different characteristics involve improving the standard of electrical fitting accessories of Sargodha. The factors of education and experience in running the business are involved to improving the standard. The study suggests that the SMEs in Sargodha who have educated ability relative to others and experience in running business are successful competing in improving quality.

Similarly a study has been conducted regarding the same SME of electrical fitting accessories of Sargodha to evaluate the effect of business constraints on growth potential and performance. The constraints of Energy, Labor Regulations, Inflation and Price Instability, Bad Business Practices, Imports of Electrical Accessories, Limited Market Access, Investment Obstacles and political instability are included to evaluate their effect on growth potential. The OLS and logistic regression analysis is apply to bring out the estimations. The constraints positively affect the growth of business except political instability. Similarly the constraints of business practices, inflation and price instability, energy constraints reduce the probability of income growth of SMEs. Correlation among business constraints and growth is also carried out through Pearson correlation matrix.

2.6 Literature review regarding Sillanwali SMEs

Sillanwali handicrafts are well known due to its unique and geometric base designs of products. In context to Sillanwali, some studies had been conducted regarding its importance and way of contribution as a livelihood perspective. These studies are survey base conducted to explore the knowledge, skills and market situation of respective area.

The wood craft and carpentry profession in Sillanwali attributed with knowledge, skills and technique has been study by (Ejaz, 2013). The study measure and analyze the descriptive statistics in order to explore the Sillanwali artisans work. Skills, knowledge, techniques and tools are the major factors of artisan work identify by the study. The sample size is consisting of 45 respondents from which formal or informal way of methods use for questioning. The study is an anthropological attempt with qualitative nature of data. The study explains the research results in four ways; opinion regarding adaptation of occupation, duration till adoption of occupation, responses on acquired occupation and opinion about skill acquisition. The study use different responses factors to questioning regarding all these four forms. The results of study show that the adaptation of business or artisan work is majorly due to economic needs not due to interest in respective field. The skills and techniques which are traditional in nature are passing upon next generation from their ancestors and due to this access to global markets, new designs and knowledge about profitable ways of earning are always be factors involve in hindrance the industrial growth.

Sargodha Chamber of Commerce (SCCI) is an auxiliary department of government who is responsible for uplifting the local industry termed as Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. The efforts regarding primary analysis base on collaboration by stakeholders and their associations, a survey had been conducted by (Iqbal, 2010) under the headship of SCCI in respect to Sillanwali handicrafts. The purpose of survey was due to pay main attention by R& D department of SCCI along with other government institutions and NGOs to point out problems and their solution face by Sillanwali handicrafts sector. The focus was to provide a scientific base of production to this cluster by means of providing accessing in solving concerned issues. The survey provided with a list of problems; lack of education, technological problems, raw material availability issue, unclear definition of industry, low demand, unexplored export markets, bad business practices and religious hazards which are major contributors to hindrance growth of this cluster. The study also provides an information that is based upon SWOT analysis showing strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats to Sillanwali handicraft sector. The survey study results also provide an export variations and competition scenario of Sillanwali handicrafts cluster in context with other competing countries.

A diagnostic study conducted by AHAN (2008) developed under UNIDO Cluster Development Programme Pakistan. The study was conducted regarding lacquer art work in Sillanwali. The study points out some lacquer art products and measures their sale prices by describing different processes of costing attributed to become a sale price. The study also focuses on issues faced by lacquer art production in the Sillanwali cluster. This sector includes problems and issues; Technological issues, design and product issues, marketing issues and accessing issues. The study also shows SWOT analysis and provides with basic assessment and supportive policies.

2.7 Summary of Literature Review

So, it is concluded that SMEs at national and international level are badly affected by business constraints. Due to these constraints income growth and profit share of firms are at decline situation. Accessing of finance is an important problem for small enterprises that hinders their business growth. The firms have innovative perspectives in their products and easily compete at international markets by improving their sales. While the literature also suggests some firm level factors that are responsible for a firm to increase the probability to access the finance.

3. METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

This section discusses the effect of business constraints on growth potential and performance of Sillanwali SMEs in theoretical framework. The section also represents research methods, empirical models, data collection techniques, sample size, target population and source of data.

3.1 Business constraints

To achieve the objectives of the study regarding business constraints and their effect on SMEs growth, following constraints are taken under consideration. The constraints include basic education, shortage of electricity, transportation, tax rates, tax administration, technology & firm innovation, skills & education of workers, accessing & cost of financing, political instability, inflation & price instability, demand uncertainty & lack of customers, severe competition, unaffordability of CNC machines and inefficient cost of electricity. The explanation of these constraints is discussed below.

3.1.1 Basic education

Education is a fundamental objective of any country to strive for success. As it is important to improve standard of living and helps to achieve high ranks in any society. In SMEs, workers are laboring for their livelihood. The problem of illiteracy is attributed to these workers as majority of them have not even primary level education. Due to this, they are unable to understand basic rules and regulations of labor. The organization takes advantage of these illiterate workers and pays the worker with a wage,

which is not appropriate according to labor regulations in Pakistan. Moreover, due to illiteracy, workers get loans from their landlords at high interest rate and children after their parents are bound to work in particular SME for years in order to repay loans. In this way, the worker who has ability to work in an innovative SME is bound to work in traditional SME. Due to this, skill full human capital wasted due to illiteracy as workers have less sense of utilization their skills in a profitable way.

3.1.2 Shortage of electricity

Electricity is important for carrying out economic activities and production of SMEs. In Pakistan, the shortage of electricity is a major problem to local SMEs. Because SMEs operations depend upon electricity as the instruments and devices used in manufacturing process rely upon availability of electricity. In Sillanwali, the process of producing handicraft items involves of multi-process units. From cutting of wood to furnishing of product, different mechanical processes are operating on electricity. The shortage of electricity leads to reduce the production volume of Sillanwali SMEs. Due to this, the deliveries of orders receive from across the national and international markets badly affected by decreasing in production and affect the growth of business.

3.1.3 Transportation constraint

In industrial sector, the transportation process is very important to carry out day to day production activities. In Sillanwali SMEs, transportation is very important for transporting different items to a one place for purpose of manufacturing. These items include of wood, carving materials and lacquer art coloring packs etc. In producing of one product, about 10% product cost is additive of transportation cost. It means a product has average cost of 155 rupee become of 170 rupee after adding of transporting cost. In this way, additional cost as a transportation cost must be bear by producer as well as customer. This act leads to decrease the profit margin and accessing of products to new markets for purpose of selling.

3.1.4 Tax rates and tax administration

In Pakistan, the small business is always exploited by putting high tax percentages on production. Federal Bureau of Revenue (FBR) in order to increase tax collection tries to implement high taxes on business sector. SMEs are among those enterprises which are badly affected by tax rates. From the raw materials to final processing, each and every item is tax affected. In Sillanwali SMEs, taxes have been charged under different heads i.e. sales tax, income tax and labor tax. These taxes are collected from SMEs according to their sales, productions, freight charges and hiring of labor for work. The electricity cost is also a type of tax that include of tax percentage instead of any relief to SMEs. According to income slabs provided by FBR, an annual income exceeding 4 lac is liable to pay income tax of 17% in the case of tax non-Filer and 10% in the case of tax filer. This percentage and additional tax amount increase by increase in income and effect the growth of business. The SMEs as backbone of any country should be exempted from such means of tax invasion. The tax administration is liable in its rules and regulations to subsidies general public and especially the production sector like SMEs. But due to mismanagement and inappropriate information regarding local industry, tax administration has not sound policies of providing relief to these SMEs.

Labor taxes are also a part of tax bear by firm which is indirectly charged from workers. According to labor tax regulations, SME is liable to pay an amount of 1000 rupee for each worker. The SME is bound to pay this tax, otherwise it may be shut down or seal by authorities. In Sillanwali SMEs, producers are in fear regarding taxes. The fear is due to a survey conducted by PSIC in the area of Sillanwali about 12 years ago. In this survey, some specific questions regarding production, sales and monthly/annually income were answered by SMEs owners. At that point, SMEs in Pakistan were at its peak in production due to strong sound policies by government and better accessing of finance. So, the income and sales

along with production were also high among Sillanwali SMEs. After getting data regarding SMEs income, production and sales, PSIC in collaboration with FBR implement high taxes on the SMEs. This act badly affected the production and growth of Sillanwali SMEs. Majority of the SMEs stopped their business and many of medium enterprises reduced to small enterprises. Many workers also migrated from SMEs sector to privately owned cart system. It indicates that, highly skilled labor transforms from profitable sector to low profit system. So, SMEs were badly affected by these high taxes and institutional mismanagement. This act of tax invasion is still responsible to current decline situation of SMEs growth in Sillanwali.

3.1.5 Technology and firm innovation

In 21st century, technology has a major contribution to growth perspective of any country. Pakistan is a developing country which has great source of human capital but it is unable to utilize it at optimal level by using technological advancement. Moreover, Pakistan is among those countries that have less development in the field of technology. Technology is an important component to develop SME sector. Technology directly and indirectly helps to specialize idle resources in a productive output by reducing the cost and time constraints. Technology is important to SMEs due to its ability of introducing unique and design oriented products. It helps in producing high range of products with maximum utilization of resources. Unfortunately, in Pakistan technology is an absent feature especially in local SMEs. Sillanwali SMEs are also lacking in the feature of technology because this industry still operates at traditional level. Here, the traditional ways of wood cutting, carving, lacquer art and furnishing are dominant in production process. The different manufacturing instruments used in Sillanwali handicraft SMEs are *Neeha, Nihan, Mathan, Addi, Sathra, Verma/Berma, Tesha, Aari, Ret and Rengatha* that are traditional in nature. All these instruments are used in the process of wood works and have no technological characteristic. Due to this, it take time and lot of expenditures to make any product that is unique and oriented in its aspects. Moreover, it is difficult to make high range of products those have characteristics of innovation and technological improvement. So, absence of technology is a main constraint to business growth.

3.1.6 Skills and education of workers

After establishment of education commission in Pakistan, education was considered as a one of key priority to make substantial investment in the human capital. Education helps to develop a knowledge base society through well standard way of research and skill full activities. SMEDA, after its establishment also tries to provide basic education and skills to workers of SMEs. For this purpose, it designs practice base policies to uplift SME sector of Pakistan. But due to political influence and instability of economic activities, SMEs are still lacking in skills and educational perspectives. Without skill labor and education, it is difficult for SMEs to operate at optimal level.

3.1.7 Accessing and cost of financing

Accessing of finance and cost of financing are major constraints that affect the growth of SMEs in Pakistan. The growth of any industry relies on capital and investment of finance in production process. SMEs in Pakistan always face the shortage of finance and if finance is available it is at high cost of interest rate. Due to this, it became difficult for local SMEs to increase the production and capital base investment. Sillanwali handicraft sector has also constraint of accessing the finance. SME bank, Microfinance banks, Kashf foundation, AHAN and Akhuwat foundation are major formal institutions that provide loan base financing to Sillanwali handicraft sector. But the accessibility of finance through these sources is very complicated due to difficulties in procedural process. In order to get finance from these sources, a person will be liable to repay loan with a fixed amount of interest along with number of guarantees. So, the amounts including of interest rates and guarantees are cost of financing for SME

which creates hindrance in accessing of finance.

3.1.8 Inflation and price instability

Inflation represents the rate of increase in prices of goods and services. In Pakistan, high inflation rate causes instability in economy due to shocking oil prices and unstable exchange rates. Pakistan experienced historically high inflation rate of 24.3% during FY 2009 (*Economic Survey of Pakistan*, 2016). Instability in prices leads to high inflation rate that directly effects the industrial growth. SME sector is also badly effect by high inflation rate because it leads to expensive of products and burden has to face by both the producer and consumer. In Sillanwali SMEs instability of prices leads to decrease the sales and producer tries to reduce its production.

3.1.9 Political instability

Investment in SME sector is badly affected by political instability because of its negative impact on foreign investment in SME sector. The political instability in government policies and regulations regarding SMEs, leads to create uncertainty behavior for foreign investors and producers. Moreover, issues of strikes, favoritism and bad business practices are also exist due to political instability. In case of Sillanwali SMEs, political instability is among those constraints which are responsible for decline growth of business. The handicraft items which are exported to other countries badly affect by strikes as the containers carry handicraft products stopped at different cities due to blockage of roads. Due to this, there is a delay in delivering of order at international boarder within specific time period. It results to cancel out the orders and whole loss has faced by producers. This act of loss creates discourage attitude in producers and investors for future investment.

3.1.10 Demand uncertainty and lack of customers

In SME sector, production depends upon demand of products. If there is no demand for products, it leads to reduce production by SME. Moreover, some portion of SMEs production is also exported at international level. But, due to poor policy management and irregularities regarding rules implementation, there is reduction in demand of products at national and international level. Due to this, there is excess in supply of products and loss is bear by producer. In case of Sillanwali SMEs, due to limited market access and less opportunities to access new markets, demand of handicraft products is always low.

3.1.11 Severe competition

In the era of technological advancement, competition is an important factor that affects the sales and production of any industry. In all over the world, competition is a main factor that is responsible to create differentiated products by firms. On the basis of products differentiation and uniqueness, a buyer may prefer one product to other. Finance and investment are important components to generate competitive atmosphere among SMEs in Pakistan. The small firms have shortage of finance to carry its production activities. Due to this they have limited ability to hire efficient labor and produce large range of products whereas, large firms have finance for investment that helps to produce large range of unique products. These products capture the attention of buyers which ultimately increases the sales of large firms irrespective to small firms. This act diminishes the sales of small firms and a competition arose among SME sector. Similarly, competition hindrance the sales and profit margin of small enterprises.

In case of Pakistan, SME sector has limited access to new markets at international level. It is due to manufactured products that have low quality and absence of innovation base designs in products. In reference to SMEs of Sillanwali, severe competition is major problem to business. SMEs that are operating in Sillanwali classify as small enterprises and shop base enterprises according to number of employees work in it. The small enterprises are dominant on shop base enterprises due to their

tendency of modifying products in order to increase range of goods. Due to this, the range of products and profit of dominant firm's increases and shop base SMEs remain at their initial level of low profit and products designing.

Moreover, if shop base SMEs try to compete with dominant firms they have to invest beyond their tendency, which ultimately affect their profit margin and environment of competition develop between firms. The handicraft products also exports at international level and compete with rivalry competitors such as India. Today in regionally competitive atmosphere, India has strong hold in supply handicrafts products across the world due to proper and efficient way of providing oriented base unique items. So, there is need of attention upon policies and competitive trends in relation to handicrafts sector of Pakistan.

3.1.12 Un-affordability of CNC machines and inefficient cost of electricity

Pakistan SMEs sector is lacking in production of unique items as compare to other regional and international competing countries. Un-affordability of local producers to purchase CNC machines is main cause of limited production. CNC machines are actually computed integration base machines that can easily to operate and automatically cut the wood in designs with short span of time. These machines are efficient in saving time and labor. Moreover, with limited utilization of raw materials, large amount of products can made. Directly or indirectly labor cost, excess utilization of resources, cost of electricity, higher cost of cutting by traditional tools, limited process of manufacturing and delay in order can be easily avoided through usage of CNC machines. Specific to handicrafts sector, SMEs have shortage of capital and due to higher cost of purchasing CNC machines, production level always trending decline in Pakistan. It is responsibility of government to restrict this issue by providing duty free manageable computed machines so that production level can be easily improve by SMEs sector. The cost of electricity is also a constraint to Sillanwali SMEs because of charging high cost that include of tariff and tax. After using every hundred units, tax and tariff margin increases. In Pakistan, operating system of SMEs depends upon traditional machines rather than CNC machines. Traditional machines consume higher amount of electricity and due to which SMEs have to pay large amount of electricity bill.

3.2 Some challenges to Sillanwali handicraft SMEs

The study investigates problems which are associated with handicrafts sector in Sillanwali by conducting the pilot study regarding issues and problems faced by SMEs. Some challenges and problems are discussed as following

3.2.1 Union voting and its issues

Small and medium enterprises are working under some rules and regulations provided through legislative framework. These rules define the legalization and proper establishment of business by creating unions. The safety risks, high taxation duties, weaker formalization of employment conditions, low wages suggest that SMEs should get benefit from membership of union and collective bargaining. So, SMEs of Sillanwali establish union to ensure their rights of business.

In SMEs, unions are established under two forms; Formal form of union and Informal form of union. Formal form includes of selection criteria among elected candidates through voting process while family unions, group unions and cartel unions include to informal form of union.

In Sillanwali SMEs, formal form of union is used for selection process. The President, Vice president, general Secretary and secretary finance along committee members are selected for tenure of 3 to 4 years. In voting process, all member SMEs have equal right to vote for specific post. But in Sillanwali SMEs, a particular issue of union voting is identifying by current study. In the selection of union and its members, the vote is only cast only by those firms who have at least 3 workers to be worked in firm. While, the firms having 1 to 2 workers are not permissible to used right of voting for any party. So, due

to this issue, the values of courage, self-respect, motivation to success and efficiency of work diminish and results to decrease the business growth of SMEs.

3.2.2 Technology issue

In Sillanwali SMEs, the manufacturing process is traditional in nature and advancement of technology is one of the major issue faces by these firms. Advancement in technology helps to increase the production of a specific firm and also helpful in reducing the time as well as cost of production. In the case of Sillanwali SMEs, technology is expensive to obtain for manufacturing process due to deficiency in investment and profit margin. Moreover, the people work in Sillanwali SMEs has expertise of using traditional methods of manufacturing process and they are less educated to operate technology base machines. The reason is that, there is inherited transformation of traditional skills from ancestors to new generation. It is a need of time for government to step forward in order to provide initial training to workers regarding use of technological base machines. Moreover, the technological base machines should be less costly and affordable for a general SME having investment and financial constraints.

3.2.3 Loans and grants issue

Government provides assistance to SMEs regarding accessing to finance by providing loans and grants. Financial institutions are major contributor to distribute finance in the form of loans and grants to a needed SME. The organizational and procedural mismanagement is involved in distributional process which makes difficult the accessibility of finance to SMEs. The current study identifies the issues of finance accessibility by asking the question regarding loans and grants taken from government by a respondent.

According to answers by 80% respondents, Punjab Small Industries Corporation (PSIC) is an assisting institute that distributes grants and loans from government to general SME. The corruption and bribery factor is dominant in its distribution process due to which small SMEs badly affected by shortage of finance. According to respondents, about 2 years ago PSIC provides soft term loans to Sillanwali SME for investing purpose. Under this scheme, a loan of 2 lac was given to an SME and a grant of sixty thousands to a *dastighar*. The purpose of providing loans to this sector was due to government efforts to increase employment status of respective area and helped to increase the profit ratio of SMEs.

In order to manage time constraint faced by PSIC authorities, they made collaboration with large SMEs that were operating in Sillanwali. PSIC gave loans to these SMEs instead of small SMEs and small SMEs again deprived off from financing.

3.2.4 PSIC and tax rate issue

Punjab Small Industries Corporation is auxiliary institute of government operating at different cities of Pakistan. The branches of PSIC are functional in Lahore, Faisalabad, Rawalpindi, Bahawalpur, Multan and Islamabad. These branches are known as "Pakistan Handicrafts Centers". These branches are considered as one place for selling and purchasing of handicraft items. The manufacturers and sellers come at these centers to selling out their products. The current study identifies a problem regarding selling of handicraft items at these centers. When sellers go to sale their handicraft items they have to pay some amount of tax to these branches. These branches collect the tax on behalf of PSIC. The tax amount which is charged on products differs from person to person depending on person tax filer or non-filer status. For a non-filer person, the tax is about 8% of total selling while 4% from a non-filer person. Moreover, seller is also bound to give 2-5% commission as a bribe to different persons involved in selling purchasing process. So, this act negatively affects the profit of firm and responsible to decline profit ratio Sillanwali SMEs.

3.2.5 Labor tax issue

Labor taxes and regulations are implementing for securing interest of workers by the government.

Punjab Labor Authority is a government institution which is working for securing the welfare of workers. The authorities implement taxes on the industries under category of labor tax and this tax is used for welfare of workers. The current study identifies a problem regarding labor tax in situation of Sillanwali handicrafts. About 2 years ago, Punjab Labor Authority surveyed SMEs of Sillanwali and put tax on firm under head of labor tax. The tax was an amount of Rs800 – 1000 for each worker that must be paid by owner per month. The owner of SME after paid tax directly detects the amount of Rs1000 from the salary of workers. Due to this issue many workers left the handicraft SMEs and whole industry deprived from skillful workers

3.3 Sources of data

For current study primary data has been collected through detailed survey of handicrafts manufacturing SMEs in Sillanwali. The sample size consists of 120 firms and data is collected through well-structured questionnaire. The study used stratified random sampling by dividing the SMEs of Sillanwali in two stratum; colonial areas and block areas.

3.4 Models and estimation techniques

The main focus of the study is threefold; firstly estimate the impact of firm level characteristics on accessing of finance. Secondly estimate the impact of business constraints on performance of firm. Thirdly estimate the impact of business constraints on growth potential of firm. In order to achieve the objectives of study, ordinary least squares regression model and logistic regression model have been estimated.

In order to measure accessing of finance by SME, a question regarding firm accessing of finance (DAF) is asked from sample SMEs (i.e.; whether they have problem in accessing the finance=1, or they have no problem in accessing the finance=0). The responses from respondents are used as a proxy to measure the accessing of finance.

In order to evaluate performance of SMEs, a question regarding the sales of SMEs per month (salepm) is asked from sample SMEs (i.e., whether the income of SME increased=1, or income of SME decreased/remain constant=0). The responses from firms are used as proxy to evaluate performance of SMEs.

Similarly, in order to assess the growth potential of sample SMEs, a question regarding income situation is asked (i.e. whether in previous five years income increase=1, or whether in previous five years income decrease/remain constant =0). The responses are used as proxy to check the growth potential of sample SMEs.

Following logistic regression model is estimated to check the impact of firm level characteristics on accessing of finance by sample SMEs and taking access to finance (DAF) as categorical dependent variable. SME conditional expectation of accessing of finance given explanatory variables firm size, firm age, capital, sales and collateral are;

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Model 1: } P(DAF_{prob} = 1 | DFS_i, DFA_i, DK_i, DSALE_i, DCOLL_i) \\ = F(\beta_0 + \beta_1 DFS_i + \beta_2 DFA_i + \beta_3 DK_i + \beta_4 DSALE_i + \beta_5 DCOLL_i) \end{aligned}$$

Where,

DAF is categorical response variable which is equal to 1, if firm has problem in accessing the finance and 0 otherwise. The model includes five major firm level characteristics on the basis of group discussion with stakeholders and through literature review. These characteristics include of firm size, firm age, capital, sales, collateral and used them as dummy explanatory variables. The variable of firm size is categorize as 0 and 1 (i.e. 1= if number of employees in firm are greater than or equal to 15, 0=

otherwise). The variable of firm age is categorized as 0 and 1 (i.e. 1= if firm has been operated from greater than or equal to 35 years, 0= otherwise). The variable of capital is also categorized as 0 and 1 (i.e. 1= if firm has capital greater than or equal to amount of 4 lac, 0=otherwise). For variable of sales, 1= if firm has monthly sales greater than or equal to 8 lac, 0=otherwise. While, the variable of collateral is equal to 1, if firm has any collateral requirements to access of finance, 0= otherwise.

An OLS regression model is estimated to check the performance of SMEs and taking sales per month (salespm) as dependent variable. The model is as below,

$$\text{Model 2: } \text{salespm}_i = \beta_0 + \beta_{1j} \text{BusConst}_{ij} + \beta_{2t} \text{ControlVar}_{it} + \varepsilon_i$$

Where *salespm* represents the sales of particular firm per month and indicates the performance of firm, β' 's shows the parametric values respective explanatory variables. The term *i* represents the number of firms ($i=1, 2, 3 \dots 120$). *j* represents the number of constraints that are included in model ($j=1, 2, \dots 9$). The term *t* represents the number of control variables that are included in model ($t=1, 2, 3$). The symbol ε represents the error term.

3.4.1 Description of variables

The model includes nine business constraints that affect the performance of firm. The constraints include in study by reviewing of literature and discussion with stakeholders. Access of finance, cost of financing, tax rates, tax administrations, inflation and price instability, political instability, un-affordability of CNC machines, inefficient cost of electricity and severe competitions are major constraints effect the performance of SMEs in Sillanwali. Moreover, these constraints are included in model by considering them as index number and treated as continuous variables.

The business constraints of "accessing of finance" and "cost of finance" capture the effect of problems that a firm has to face in order to accessing the finance. The constraints of "Inflation & price instability" and "Political instability" are included in model to capture the effect of instable input prices and inflationary effect due to unstable exchange rates. The constraints of "tax rate" and "tax administration" are included to check the effect of inappropriate tax policies and high tax rate invasion in Sample SMEs. The constraint of "severe competition" captures the effect of competition that arises among enterprises at national and international level. The business constraints of "unaffordable of CNC machines" and "inefficient cost of electricity" are included to capture the irresponsible behavior of government regarding lack of providing subsidies to SME sector for advancement of technology in processing machines of sample SMEs.

For constraint of "accessing of finance" a question is asked to sample SMEs, whether accessing of finance is problem for your business or not. If respondent answer as yes then further question regarding severity of constraint is asked and answer is taken on five point Likert scale (i.e. Either the constraint is severe, major, minor, moderate or no effect on your business). The responses regarding constraint severity are included in model as an index number equal to 4 if accessing of finance is severe problem to business, 3 if it is major problem to business, 2 if it is moderate problem to business, 1 if it is minor problem to business and 0 if it is no problem to business.

For constraints of cost of financing, tax rates, tax administration, inflation & price instability, political instability, un-affordability of CNC machines, inefficient cost of electricity, severe competition same procedure is adopted by asking the question whether the constraint is problematic to your business or not. If yes, then severity of constraint is checked on five point Likert scale ranging from 0 to 4.

The variables of firm age, firm size and capital are used as control variables and they also affect the performance of firm. These variables take as continuous and capture the effect of firm level characteristics on performance of Sillanwali SMEs. The variable of firm age takes as continuous variable

by asking the question from firms about their date/year of establishment. The firm age is important in reference to check performance of firm because a firm that is established from a long period of time has an advantage of utilizing inputs in a profitable way on the basis of experience. Experience with the passage of time make a firm capable to take better decisions and implement sound policies of management. So, the firm age has direct influenced on the performance of a firm in order to manage its production activities in a profitable way.

Firm size is another important variable that affect the performance of firm. For accessing the firm size, a question is asked to SMEs about number of employees that are working in SME. The firm's answers take as continuous and included in model. Similarly, the variable of capital is also used as continuous variable by asking the question to SMEs regarding their capital.

Now the model 2 after including business constraints and control variables can be written as;

$$\begin{aligned} salespm_i = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 AFF_i + \beta_2 ACF_i + \beta_3 TR_i + \beta_4 TA_i + \beta_5 INF_i + \beta_6 PINS_i \\ & + \beta_7 UCNC_i + \beta_8 INCE_i + \beta_9 SC_i + \beta_{10} FSize_i + \beta_{11} FAge_i + \beta_{12} K_i + \varepsilon_i \end{aligned}$$

Where;

Salespm= Sale per month

AFF= Access of Finance

ACF = Cost of Finance

TR = Tax Rate

TA = Tax Administration

INF =Inflation and Price Instability

PINS = Political Instability

UCNC =Unaffordability of CNC Machines

INCE =Inefficient Cost of Electricity

SC = Severe Competition

FSize = Firm Size

FAge = Firm Age

K = Capital of Firm

The above mathematical model is estimated through OLS regression method.

A logistic regression model is estimated to check the growth potential of SMEs. The model is estimated by making association of firm growth potential with 6 business constraints and takes growth potential (DY_{sit}) as a categorical response variable. Similarly, the conditional expectations of firm growth given explanatory variables political instability, shortage of electricity, shortage of finance, limited access to new markets, lack of government subsidies, firm innovation are;

$$\begin{aligned} Model\ 3: \quad & P(DY_{sit} = 1 | PI_i, ES_i, FC_i, LNM_i, LGS_i, DFI_i) \\ & = F(\beta_0 + \beta_1 PI_i + \beta_2 ES_i + \beta_3 FC_i + \beta_4 LNM_i + \beta_5 LGS_i + \beta_6 DFI_i) \end{aligned}$$

Where DY_{sit} is referred as growth potential of sample SMEs by asking the question regarding income of firm during previous five years. The response from sample SME is then categorize as 1, if income of firm increase in previous five years, 0=otherwise.

All these business constraints are used as explanatory variables and their values take as continuous by making the index numbers ranging from 0 to 4. The respondent is asked about whether the constraint is a problem for your business or not. If yes, then severity of constraint is checked on five Likert scale that is equal to 4, if problem is severe to business, 3=if problem is major to business, 2= if problem is moderate to business, 1=if problem is minor to business and 0= if it is no problem to business. The

business constraints along with symbols and effectiveness are discussed in table 2.

Table 02 Business constraints and their effectiveness

Sr. #	Constraint name	Symbol	Effectiveness
1	Political instability	PI	Capturing the effect of economic instability
2	Electricity shortage	ES	Capturing the effect of unavailability of electricity and inappropriate cost of electricity
3	Finance constraint	FC	Capturing the combine effect of Access of finance + Cost of financing
4	Limited access to new markets	LNLM	Capturing the effect of limited access of sample SMEs in new national and international markets
5	Lack of government subsidies	LGS	Capturing the effect of government inappropriate policies to provide subsidies in sample SMEs
6	Firm Innovation	FI	Capturing the combine effect of Firm inability to produce innovative items due to lack of technological improvement

3.5 Logistic regression model

The logit model is important in its nature as rather modeling the dependent variable directly (e.g., finding the expected value of dependent variable Y , for some values of independent variables X_i), it estimate the probability that $Y=1$. The procedure of logit model is same to simple regression model as we assume different sets of independent variables to predict dependent variable but in logit we are claiming that this variable predict the probability of $Y=1$. The basic formula for estimating $Y=1$, consists of transforming the regression equation as;

$$P(Y = 1) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp[-1(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k)]}$$

In the given logit function, denominator in parentheses like regression model but it is transform in an unusual way. The part is multiplied by -1, exponent, added to 1 and then inverted. This function is called logistic function and it is estimated through maximum likelihood (ML) technique. So, in this way, the given function guarantees to be bounded values of categorical dependent variable between 0 and 1. Thus, the applicability of logit model provides a solution to avoid biased results due to violation of OLS assumptions (Hoffman).

3.6 Summary

So, it is concluded that, there are 12 main business constraints which are responsible to negatively affect the growth and performance of SMEs. The current source of data is obtained from 120 handicraft SMEs of Sillanwali and two models are designed to check the effect of business constraints on performance

and income growth situation of sample SMEs. All the business constraints are taken as continuous variables for analysis by considering them as index number ranging from 0-4. The study also includes a model regarding variables of firm level characteristics i.e. firm age, firm size, sales, capital, collateral in order to check the percentage of probability to accessing the finance. The method of OLS and logistic regression are utilized for quantitative analysis.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section discusses the results regarding the effect of business constraints on performance and growth potential of SMEs. The responses regarding the severity of business constraints are also graphically shown in this section. Section 4.2 discusses the graphical representation regarding the severity of business constraints. Section 4.3 discusses the empirical interpretation of results. Section 4.4 discusses the anthropological interpretation of Sillanwali SMEs. Section 4.5 discusses the export opportunities for SMEs of Sillanwali and Pakistan.

4.1 Graphically interpretation

4.1.1 Basic education

Basic education is necessary for workers to be familiar with laws and regulations, which are important for working in any organization. Without basic education they cannot be able to defend their rights. Basic education covers the primary level education of workers, which enables them to make wage calculations and come to know about basic formalities required for work in any SME.

Figure 6 Basic education

Source: Author's own calculation

In case of Sillanwali handicraft SMEs, the question regarding the constraint of basic education has been answered by SMEs (either basic education is a constraint to business growth or not). If the respondent answers YES, then the answer is classified on a 5-point Likert scale according to the severity of the constraint to business. The scale ranging from 0-4 comprises of 4=Very Severe constraint, 3=Major constraint, 2=Moderate constraint, 1=Minor constraint, 0=No constraint. Figure 6 shows the 120 respondents' answers regarding the severity of the constraint. According to 94% of firms, basic education is not a problem for their business, while 3% consider basic education as a major and moderate constraint to business respectively. The firms consider basic education not a severe problem for SMEs of Sillanwali. It is also interpreted from Figure 6 that in Sillanwali SMEs; the workers have at least a primary level of education. Moreover, it has also been investigated that rules and regulations are easily understandable by employees due to which it is easy for workers to get the benefits of employment.

4.1.2 Shortage of electricity

Electricity is necessary for carrying out economic activities as industrial output highly depends upon availability of electricity. In Pakistan, shortage of electricity is an issue to industrial sector due to which industrial output is still lagging behind in producing variety of products. The sample SMEs also considered shortage of electricity as a major problem to the business.

Figure 7 Shortage of electricity

Source: Author's own calculation

The figure 7 represents the percentage of firm's answers regarding constraint of electricity shortage. According to 23% firms, shortage of electricity is a severe constraint to business while 43% consider shortage of electricity as major constraint to business growth. About 26% firms consider it moderate constraint to business. Similarly, 7% and 1% firms consider it as minor and no constraint to business respectively.

4.1.3 Tax rates and tax administration

Taxes are necessary to generate revenue in any economy. But high tax rate creates irregularities in production process because it leads to reduce industrial output. This is due to the tax affected materials which are used in manufacturing process of SMEs.

In Pakistan, high taxes affected the SMEs growth because of limited resources and high tax percentages on manufactured products. Moreover, government instead of providing support and subsidies to SME sector always tries to increase tax rates on industrial output in order to increase its tax revenue. According to SMEs high tax rates are severe problem to their business. In figure 8, 98% firms consider tax rates as a severe problem to their business while only 2% consider it as major problem to business growth.

Similarly, tax administration departments are responsible to manage and implement taxes that should be rational and helping in growth of SME sector. But regarding Sillanwali SMEs, tax administration causes negative effect on business growth. The administration has no proper information regarding local industry and tries to implement high taxes on industrial output. The figure 9 shows firm's answers regarding tax administration constraint. About 90% firms consider it as severe problem to business and 8% consider it as major constraint to business. While 2% consider it as a moderate problem to business.

Figure 8 Tax rates

Source: Author's own calculation

Figure 9 Tax administration

Source: Author's own calculation

So, the current study infers that according to 95% firm's tax rates and tax administration are severe problems to business. These two constraints negatively affect the growth of business in Sillanwali SMEs and reflect the irrational policies of government regarding small business.

4.1.4 Accessing and cost of financing

Accessing of finance is a main problem to SMEs growth. Finance availability is necessary to develop industrial sector as it is main source of investment in small business. SMEs are main sector of any economy for purpose of investment but accessing of finance by SMEs is restrictive due to complicated procedures and formalities. These formalities consist of collateral requirements, existing capital of firm, assets of firm and guarantees in the form of cheques and pay orders. All these formalities negatively affect the accessing of finance by firms and therefore, they have shortage of finance for investment purposes.

Figure 10, shows SMEs answers regarding severity of constraint. About 49% firms, it is severe problem to the business while 33% consider it as no problem to business growth. 11%, 5% and 3% firms consider it as major, moderate and minor problem to the business respectively. Thus, the current study identifies that constraint of accessing the finance is problematic to the SMEs of Sillanwali due to strict formalities and procedures by financial institutions. Moreover, due to shortage of finance, mostly SMEs of Sillanwali are unable to scale up their production that ultimately results to decline in profit margin.

Figure 10 Access of financing

Source: Author's own calculation

Similarly, the cost of financing covers the side of cost which can be bear by SME in order to get finance. High interest rates, complex application procedures, and maturity of loans are main costs of financing attribute to Sillanwali SMEs growth. The main institutes to provide loans in Sillanwali SMEs are commercial banks, Microfinance institutes, AHAN, Akuwat and Kashf foundations. These institutes provide loans but their requirements make it difficult to obtain it. Different documentations, high interest rates and guarantees are issues attach to these institutions that cause hindrance to accessing the finance in Sillanwali SMEs. These costs in the form of formalities are unaffordable by majority of SME owners because about 70 percent of SMEs are poor or their affordability to fulfill these requirements is not easily accessible by them.

Figure 11 Cost of financing

Source: Author's own calculation

According to figure 11, about 67% firms consider cost of financing as severe constraint to their business. While 21%, 3%, 1% and 8% firms consider it as major, moderate, minor and no constraint to their business respectively.

4.1.5 Inflation and price instability

Inflation refers to persistent rise in prices of goods and services of any economy. Rise in prices decrease the production as it leads to reduce demand of products. The SMEs of Sillanwali have great potential to increase range of products and also have an ability to contribute large share in local employment. According to sample SMEs of Sillanwali, inflation is a severe problem to their business because output

that they produce becomes expensive due to rise in prices of raw materials. Moreover, due to expensive output, the exports become costly that badly affects the export volume of products.

Figure 12 represents the respondent's answers regarding constraint of inflation and price instability. Graphical representation supports the severity of constraint in the case of Sillanwali SMEs, by showing 91% firms that consider it as severe constraint to business growth. About 6% consider inflation as major constraint while 3% consider it as moderate constraint to their business.

Figure 12 Inflation and price instability

Source: Author's own calculation

4.1.6 Political instability

Political instability negatively effects the growth of small business. Strikes, wars, poor law and order conditions create situation of political instability in any country. Due to these issues, export volume reduces and firms have no access to new international markets. Regarding the case of Sillanwali SMEs, political instability is a severe problem to business growth.

Figure 13 Political instability

Source: Author's own calculation

The Figure 13 shows the graphical representation of political instability in the case of Sillanwali SMEs. 71% firms consider political instability as severe constraint following by 22% considers it as major constraint to business. About 1%, 3% and 4% firms consider political instability as moderate, minor and no constraint for their business.

4.1.7 Severe competition

Competition is necessary to create range of products that are different in designs and patterns with

respect to each other. But competition in SMEs hindrance the growth of business as it exploits small SMEs by boost up sales of large enterprises. Large enterprises have tendency to utilize technology and capital in better means which enable them to produce unique products as compare to small SMEs. Competition negatively affects the business as small producers exploit by the large producers.

In case of Sillanwali SMEs, 70% of SMEs are small in nature and they have limited finance to make investment in business. According to SMEs, competition is severe problem to business. In figure 14, 92% firms consider it as severe problem following by 6% firms who consider it as a major and moderate problem to their business respectively.

Figure 14 Severe competition

Source: Author's own calculation

4.1.8 Unaffordability of CNC machines

In Sillanwali SMEs, traditional machines are used for designing and manufacturing of products. Traditional ways of production increase the cost and consume a lot of time in manufacturing process. CNC machines are computer base machines that can increase the production and help to save time as well as cost of production.

Figure 15 Un-affordability of CNC machines

Source: Author's own calculation

Figure 15 shows the sample SMEs responses regarding this constraint. About 77% firms consider it as severe constraint while 15% considers it as major constraint to business. Only 8% firms consider it as moderate problem to business.

4.1.9 Inefficient cost of electricity

Similar to other constraints, the high cost of electricity is also a problem for Sillanwali SMEs. Figure 16 shows graphically the percentage of firm’s answers regarding the constraint. 71% considers it as severe constraint, 23% considers it as major constraint while 7% considers it as moderate constraint. According to respondents the machines are traditionally in nature and require high voltage of current to cut down wood into pieces. Due to high electric energy requirements, the firms have to utilize electricity at high extent which ultimately leads to increase electricity bills. For a small enterprise it is very difficult to pay high bills due to fewer profit margins.

Figure 16 Inefficient cost of electricity

Source: Author’s own calculation

4.1.10 Limited access to new markets

Due to high cost of products, the demand at international and national level becomes decline. Moreover, firms have no access to new markets for selling their products due to high cost of products. In Sillanwali SMEs, due to poor management and irresponsible behavior by government, products are producing at high cost. High cost of products is due to inflation and expensive of raw materials. About 46% firms have moderately affected by this constraint while 38% considers it as major constraint to business. The constraint negatively affects the Sillanwali SMEs as shown in figure 17.

Figure 17 Limited access to new markets

Source: Author’s own calculation

4.1.11 Lack of government subsidies

Government subsidies are important for uplifting SME sector of any country. In case of Sillanwali, the

problem of providing subsidies is severe to business. From 120 SMEs, 48% considers it as severe constraint along with 34% considering it as major constraint to business. Only 18% considers it as moderate problem affecting their growth performance and income situation of firm as shown in figure 18.

Figure 18 Lack of government subsidies

Source: Author's own calculation

The figure 19 given below shows the percentage of firms who consider these constraints as severe or major problem to business growth.

Figure 19 Percentage of all business constraints

Source: Author's own calculation

4.2 Empirical interpretation of results

Model 1

Table 3 shows the logistic regression results regarding measure the probability of accessing the finance due to firm level characteristics.

Table 3 Logit model results

Probability of accessing the finance and firm level variables (Model 1)
Logistic Regression Results

No. of observations=120			Pseudo R square= 0.58		
Variables	Exp (B)	Coefficient	Coefficient (S.E)	Significance	Log Likelihood
Firm size(d15FS)	3.422	1.23	0.992	0.215	75.608
Firm age(d35FA)	4.149	1.423	0.723	0.049	
Capital (d4lack)	17.24	2.847	3.032	0.082	
Sales (d8lacsales)	6.946	1.938	5.578	0.018	
Collateral	19.804	2.986	22.574	0.00	
Constant	0.012	-4.423	13.316	0.00	

Source: Author’s own calculation

The table 4 shows the descriptive statistics of variables measuring the effect of business constraints and control variables on performance of firm.

Table 4 Descriptive Statistics

Variables		N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Dependent variable	Sales	120	22000	1400000	3.93E+05	3.21E+05	1.03E+11
Business constraints	Tax rates	120	3	4.00	3.9833	0.12856	0.017
	Tax administration	120	2	4.00	3.8417	0.42989	0.185
	Access to financing	120	0	4.00	2.4167	1.80375	3.254
	Cost of financing	120	0	4.00	3.35	1.19979	1.439
	Inflation and price instability	120	2	4.00	3.8333	0.45528	0.207
	political instability	120	0	4.00	3.375	0.97068	0.942
	Severe competition	120	0	4.00	3.5917	0.60106	0.361

	Unaffordability of CNC machines	120	2	4.00	3.6833	0.62151	0.386
	Inefficient cost of electricity	120	2	4.00	3.6417	0.60524	0.366
Control variables	Firm size	120	2	30.00	7.8667	6.40107	40.974
	Age of firm	120	2	45.00	21.2917	11.48795	131.973
	Capital	120	20000	600000.00	1.72E+05	1.27E+05	1.62E+10

Source: Author's own Calculation

Table 5 shows the OLS regression results regarding impact of business constraints and control variables on performance of firms.

Table 5 Performance of firm and business constraints with control variables

OLS Estimation Results

Variables	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized	Test of significant		Collinearity statistics	
	Beta	S.D	Beta	t-test	Significance	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	325999	185247		1.76	0.081		
Access to financing	-28580	12312	-0.161	-2.321	0.022	0.491	2.036
Inflation and price instability	-2422	39225	-0.003	-0.062	0.951	0.759	1.317
Tax rate	-90251	146781	-0.036	-0.615	0.54	0.68	1.47
Tax administration	-4110	40437	-0.006	-0.102	0.919	0.802	1.248
Cost of financing	-27821	16409	-0.104	-1.696	0.093	0.625	1.6
Political instability	-33956	17199	-0.103	-1.974	0.051	0.869	1.151
Unaffordability of CNC machines	-73105	33812	-0.142	-2.162	0.033	0.548	1.823

Inefficient cost of electricity	-58310	29775	-0.11	-1.958	0.053	0.746	1.341
Severe competition	-52857	29517	-0.099	-1.791	0.076	0.77	1.299
Firm size	12268	4757	0.245	2.579	0.011	0.261	3.828
Age of firm	3969	1623	0.142	2.445	0.016	0.696	1.436
Capital	1.396	0.204	0.553	6.852	0.00	0.36	2.775
R square=0.75		No. of Observations =120			F- Prob = 27		

Source: Author's own calculation

In table 3 results show that all the variables of firm level characteristics have positive effect on access to finance. All the variables have significant effect on access to finance except firm size. The firms that have firm size equal to 15 or greater to it, have 3 percent more possibility to accessing the finance as compare to those firms that have firm size not equal to or greater than 15. Similarly, the variables of firm age, capital, sales and collateral has more possibility to accessing the finance regarding to their respective coefficients. The value of pseudo R square suggests that 58 percent variations is caused by firm age, firm size, capital, sales and collateral in access to finance.

In table 5, all the business constraints have negative effect on performance of firms. Similarly, all the business constraints have significant effect except tax rates, tax administration and inflation & price instability. The control variables of firm size, firm age and capital have positive and significant effect on performance of firms. The coefficient value of business constraint "access of finance" suggests that a unit increase in the index value will cause to reduce sales per month of a firm by 28589 thousands rupees. Similarly, the coefficient values of business constraints i.e. inflation & price instability, tax rates, tax administration, cost of financing, political instability, un-affordability of CNC machines, inefficient cost of electricity and severe competition suggest that a unit increase in the index values will cause to reduce sales per month of firm by their respective values.

The coefficient values of control variables i.e. firm size, firm age and capital suggest that sales of firms per month will increase by their respective values.

The model 3 measures the probability regarding growth potential of firms by considering six business constraints that badly effect the growth of SMEs in Sillanwali.

Table 6 shows logistic regression results of model 3 for analyzing income growth potential of firms. All the business constraints have negative and significant effect on growth potential of firms. A unit increase in the index value of political instability, shortage of electricity, access of finance, limited access to new markets, lack of government subsidies and firm innovation will reduce the probability of firm income growth by 44 percent, 35 percent, 60 percent, 34 percent, 44 percent and 32 percent respectively.

4.3 Anthropology base descriptive statistics of Sillanwali handicrafts

The anthropology descriptive describes the local industry culture, skills, performance and social aspects. The current study tries to find out anthropology base statistics regarding finance accessibility, number of employees, years in business, firm ownership and legal status of Sillanwali SMEs.

Table 7 shows the 120 firm's answers regarding availability of finance from different institutions in the form of loans and grants. Moreover, in order to avail finance from these institutions either a firm has provided any collateral requirements. In case of banking institutions, about 18% firms get loans from

banks while 82% does not get any type of loan from bank due to issue of high interest rate. 32% firms get grants/aids from government institutions and NGOs while 68% does not gain any type of help from these institutions. In order to get loans and grants about 31% firms have to provide collateral requirements to these institutions

Table 6 Probability of Income growth situation of firm and business constraints

Logistic Regression Model					
No. of Observations= 120			Pseudo R-square= 0.52		
Variables	Beta	S.E	Wald	Significance	Exp(Beta)
Political Instability	-0.833	0.31	7.21	0.007	0.435
Shortage of electricity	-1.065	0.336	10.043	0.002	0.345
Access of Finance	-0.519	0.167	9.681	0.002	0.595
Limited access to new markets	-1.095	0.348	9.889	0.002	0.335
Lack of government subsidies	-0.824	0.344	5.731	0.017	0.438
Firm innovation	-1.13	0.295	14.697	0.00	0.323
Constant	9.142	2	20.898	0.00	9.34E+03

Source: Author's own calculation

Table 8 shows the current sources of finance accessible by a firm. The sources of finance classified as formal and informal. Borrowed from a friend and family/relatives/inheritance income are considered as informal sources of finance to Sillanwali SMEs. Own money/saving, grants/aids from NGOs, banks & government Institutions classified as formal source of finance to Sillanwali SMEs.

Table 7 Procurement of loans from financial institutions

Financial instruments	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Banks	Yes	22	18%
	No	98	82%
Grants/Aids from any NGO or Government institution	Yes	38	32%
	No	82	68%
Collateral	Yes	37	31%
	No	83	69%

Source: Author's own calculations

Among 120 firms, 6% firm's current source of finance is borrowing from a friend. Similarly, 6% firm's current source of finance is family/relatives/inheritance income. About 88% firms are operating on finance received from government institutions and NGOs.

Table 9 shows the owned status of a SME either it is family owned business or personally owned business. About 59% firms are family owned and remaining 41% firms are personally owned. Among

these firms, only 3% firms have partnership in business.

Table 8 Current source of finance by firms

Sources	Frequency	Percentage
Borrowed from a friend	7	6%
Family/Relatives/Inheritance Income	7	6%
Own money/saving, Loan/Grant/Aid from NGOs and Banks	106	88%

Source: Author's own calculation

Table 9 Firms owned status

Ownership status	Frequency	Percentage
Family Business	71	59%
Personally owned Business	49	41%
Partnership	04	3%

Source: Author's own calculation

Table 10 Firms operating sector of production

Sector	Frequency	Percentage
Final seller	13	11%
Manufacturer	88	73%
Final seller + Manufacturer	19	16%

Source: Author's own calculations

Table 10 shows the distribution of Sillanwali SMEs according to their sector of producing items. The sector is classified as final seller, manufacturer and both a final seller and a manufacturer. About 11% firms are final sellers while 73% firms are only manufacturers which mean they are not a direct seller of handicraft products. 16% firms are operating in both sectors which mean they are manufacturers as well as final sellers of handicraft products.

Table 11 shows the number of employees that are working in Sillanwali SMEs. About 76% firms have workers less than or equal to 10. 19% firms have workers less than or equal to 20. Similarly, only 5% firms have workers less than or equal to 30.

Table 11 Number of employees in firm

Number of employees	Frequency	Percentage
Employees \leq 10	91	76%

Employees ≤ 20 >10	23	19%
Employees ≤ 30 > 20	6	5%

Source: Author's own calculation

Table 12 shows the age of firm that from how many years a particular SME is in operation. About 23% firms are operating from less than or equal to 10 years. 31% firms are operating from less than or equal to 20 years but greater than 10 years. 26% firms are operating from less than or equal to 30 years but greater than 20 years. 13% firms are operating from less than or equal to 40 years but greater than 30 years. Similarly, only 7% firms are operating from less than or equal to 50 years but greater than 40 years.

Table 12 Years of association with occupation of handicrafts

Years	Frequency	Percentage
Years ≤ 10	28	23%
Years ≤ 20 > 10	37	31%
Years ≤ 30 > 20	31	26%
Years ≤ 40 > 30	16	13%
Years ≤ 50 > 40	08	7%

Source: Author's own calculation

Table 13 Nature of business/Legal status

Business nature/ status	Frequency	Percentage
Registered (Either Union, PSIC, SCC)	78	65%
Un-registered	11	9%
Sole proprietor/Family Business	116	97%
Partnership	04	3%

Source: Author's own calculation

Table 13 shows the legal status of firms that is classified as either a firm is registered or unregistered. About 65% firms of Sillanwali handicrafts are registered through union, PSIC and SCC while only 9% firms are unregistered.

4.4 Exports opportunities to handicraft SMEs of Pakistan

Pakistan has great prospective to expand its sectors which are great source of earnings through exporting. Among these sectors are automobile instruments, surgical instruments, wool products and especially the wood items. Handicrafts are major wood items that have great potential of earnings by exporting. The study also focuses to explore potential export markets for Sillanwali wooden handicrafts. Pakistan wood products and handicraft items are well known for its sophisticated wooden artifacts on different blocks of *Sheeshum and Rosemary*. In Pakistan there are six hubs producing wooden products include of Peshawar, Karachi, Lahore, Sargodha, Chiniot and Gujrat. All these hubs are famous throughout the world for their best manufactured wooden items. Peshawar, Lahore and

Chiniot are famous in producing of wooden Furniture. Karachi is famous for handicrafts made of stones and wood. Sillanwali a tehsil of district Sargodha is famous for producing almost hundred plus handicraft items. About 30% of total Pakistan's handicraft items are exporting from Sillanwali to across the world (SMEDA). According to SMEs of Sillanwali, handicraft items are mostly exported to developed countries because developed countries have high purchasing power. All the production and exports of Pakistan wooden hubs contribute a large share in foreign earnings. The handicraft items are exporting to China, Singapore, Malaysia, UAE and other Gulf countries. Similarly, handicraft items are also exported to some European countries like London, Italy and Netherland. The top countries to which Pakistan has partnership in exporting of wood items are Iran, Afghanistan, Islamic republic of Indonesia, South Africa and Thailand (World Integrated Trade Solution, 2016). But there is a need to explore more international markets that can help to increase exports of handicraft items. There is a possibility to increase exports of handicraft items by removing the trade barriers and introduce regional base cooperation among countries.

The production of handicraft items in Pakistan can be increase by promoting local employment opportunities and income creation through access to finance for purpose of investment. Pakistan can earn number of dollars annually due to its wooden sector. The handicrafts and other wood items are classified according to their requirement and ability to purchase by a customer. Pakistan has ability to produce modify branded handicraft items, that can attract the customers and their willingness to pay for these items. It is necessary to highlight the importance of handicraft items by improving the designs, distribution process, modification in structure, and alteration in products artifacts. If compare the handicrafts of India and Pakistan, then India boost up its production of handicraft items by introducing latest processes of modification. India achieves an aggregation of amount 46 billion dollar in no time by exporting the handicraft items across the world. Exports of Pakistan handicrafts have decreasing trend due to old fashioned designs. It is necessary for Pakistan to improve its brand quality, enhance skills, improving the production and training the craftsmen. The craftsmen are primary instrument to improve by training regarding new articles of handicrafts. Pakistan has range of exports markets included of European countries, America, Central Africa and these countries are found of branded items. Pakistan should increase its exports through increasing the production of branded items in order to compete at international level.

Developed countries are improving their potential export markets by organizing the exhibitions. Exhibitions are main source of direct attraction by customer and producer. Germany organizes 1000 exhibitions annually to capture the markets for exports and motivate the local talent to utilize new processes of modification. Exhibitions are directly involved in foreign earnings as customers across the world directly involve in purchasing. The selling of handicraft items at international level is doing in two ways; online purchasing and customer interaction centers. The online websites place the handicrafts and different wood items on the website and customers place the order according to their willingness. Customer interaction centers come under the head of exhibitions where the customers directly deal with producers. So, government and semi government institutions should promote exhibitions of handicraft items that can help to access new international markets.

In Pakistan, private sector is directly involved in promoting handicraft sector. The efforts by private sector improve the well-being of economy. It is always focused to exchange views with delegations at exhibitions in order to promote economic activities. Private sector has ability to drive out notation of development. Handicrafts are the items with best earnings perspective. If the government of Pakistan try to promote the industry, then private investment automatically involve in production. Basically, handicraft SMEs are privately owned and their production totally depends upon atmosphere of loyalty

and support by government. Government is responsible to provide a proper infrastructure from processing to distribution. Investment and exhibitions along with government efforts can promote the production and able the handicraft industry to compete at international level.

It can be easily observed that all the business constraints negatively affect the performance and income growth potential of Sillanwali SMEs. The variables of firm level characteristics positively affect the performance and income growth potential of Sillanwali SMEs. The results of model 1 suggest that all the variables i.e. firm age, firm size, sales, capital and collateral increase the probability of a firm to access the finance by their respective values. The results of model 2 suggest that any unit increase in the index value of business constraints will reduce the sales of firm per month by their respective values. Similarly, the results of model 3 suggest that any unit increase in the index value of business constraints will reduce the probability of income growth potential of firm by their respective values.

In order to increase exports of handicraft products, government should organize exhibitions and reduce the trade barriers in order to promote regional cooperation between neighbor's countries. Moreover, handicraft products should be exported to European countries, USA and Middle East because the people of these countries have high purchasing power.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

SMEs as backbone of any country are responsible for uplifting the economic growth and development perspectives of industrial sector. SMEs are important to driven the path of development for any country by transforming transition based economy to a developed economy. The purpose of current study is to investigate and analyze the performance and income growth situation of SMEs in Sillanwali. The study considers that business constraints have negative effect on SMEs. The sector of handicraft SMEs in Sillanwali, a tehsil of district Sargodha, Punjab is surveyed by a well-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire includes of constraints by conducting pilot study in clusters of Sillanwali and through reviewing of literature from past research articles. The focus of study is three fold; firstly estimate the impact of firm level characteristics on accessing the finance. Secondly, estimate the impact of business constraints on performance of a firm. Thirdly estimate the impact of business constraints on growth potential of a firm. In order to achieve the objectives of study, ordinary least squares regression model and logistic regression model have been estimated.

The study includes of constraints named as access of finance, cost of financing, tax rates, tax Administration, price instability and inflation, political instability, severe competition, un-affordability of CNC machines, inefficient cost of electricity, limited access to new markets, firm innovation and lack of government subsidies. The variables of firm level characteristics named as firm age, firm size, capital, sales and collateral are also been utilized by the study.

5.2 Conclusion

The results of first model measure the probability of accessing the finance. The firm level characteristics named as firm age, firm size, capital, sales and collateral have positive effect on probability of accessing the finance. The results are interpreted as "A unit increase in firm level characteristics will increase the probability of accessing the finance by their respective values. The results of second model suggest that all business constraints have negative effect on performance of firms. Due to this, there is decline situation in business growth of Sillanwali SMEs.

The third model measures the income growth situation of Sillanwali SMEs. The results show that all the business constraints are responsible to decline of sales in Sillanwali SMEs from previous 5 years. The magnitude values of negative sign suggest that these constraints reduce the probability of firms to improve the income growth situation by increasing the sales.

5.3 Policy Recommendations

Regarding to constraints and their negative effect on Sillanwali SMEs, the study has some policy recommendations for better business growth in coming future.

- 1). The government should be responsible to support and uplifting the SMEs sector by provide sector wise financing schemes that must be operating at low interest rate policy. So, those small enterprises can easily access to finance without providing any collateral and other guarantees requirements which are mostly problematic for firms to provide.
- 2). In order to increase exports of handicraft items as they are mostly demanded by developed countries, government should manage exhibition seminars at national and international levels. The purpose of these seminars is to capture the attraction of foreign investors and purchasers which directly increase the exports and improve the socio economic conditions of a country.
- 3). In the atmosphere of competitive markets, the products having innovative designs are more demanded than any other items. So, it is need of time by government to make easy accessing to new CNC machines in order to improve designs and reduction in cost of production.
- 4). The Federal Bureau of Revenue (FBR) which is responsible to collect taxes should make flexible and smooth policies regarding SMEs tax invasion. Because, the SMEs are productive side of any country should be liable to pay less percentage of taxes on sales and production.

REFERENCES

- Abor, J., & Quartey, P. (2010). Issues in SME development in Ghana and South Africa. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 39(6), 215–228.
- Akingunola, R. O. (2011). Small and medium scale enterprises and economic growth in Nigeria: An assessment of financing options. *Pakistan Journal of Business and Economic Review*, 2(1).
- Al-Mahrouq, M. (2010). SUCCESS FACTORS OF SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES (SMEs): THE CASE OF JORDAN. *Anadolu University Journal of Social Sciences*, 10(1).
- Alper, O., & Hommes, M. (2013). *Access to Credit among Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises*. The World Bank.
- Bakar, L. J. A., & Ahmad, H. (2010). Small Medium Enterprises' Resources and the Development of Innovation in Malaysia. *Journal of Innovation Management in Small and Medium Enterprises*, 2010(2010), 1–14.
- Bari, F., & Cheema, A. (2005). *SME development in Pakistan analyzing the constraints to growth*.
- Beck, T. (2007). Financing constraints of SMEs in developing countries: Evidence, determinants and solutions. *KDI 36th Anniversary International Conference*, 26–27.
- Beck, T., & Demirguc-Kunt, A. (2006). Small and medium-size enterprises: Access to finance as a growth constraint. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 30(11), 2931–2943.
- Bhattacharya, M., & Bloch, H. (2004). Determinants of innovation. *Small Business Economics*, 22(2), 155–162.
- Dar, M. S., Ahmed, S., & Raziq, A. (2017). Small and medium-size enterprises in Pakistan: Definition and critical issues. *Pakistan Business Review*, 19(1), 46–70.
- Daskalakis, N., Jarvis, R., & Schizas, E. (2013). Financing practices and preferences for micro and small firms. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 20(1), 80–101.
- Economic Survey of Pakistan*. (2016).
- Egibiremolen, G. O., & Igberaese, F. I. (2013). Small and Medium Enterprises Financing and Economic Growth in Nigeria: An Econometric Analysis. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*,

ISSN, 1700–2222.

- Ejaz, B. (2013). WOOD CRAFT AND CARPENTRY IN SILLANWALI: EXPLORING THE KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS OF THE ARTISANS. *Training*, 24, 53.
- Ghouse, S. M. (2012). Indian handicraft industry: problems and strategies. *International Journal of Management Research and Reviews*, 2(7), 1183.
- Giacosa, E., & Mazzoleni, A. (2016). A decision model for the suitable financing for small and medium enterprises. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 8(1), 39–74.
- Hussain, J., Millman, C., & Matlay, H. (2006). SME financing in the UK and in China: a comparative perspective. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 13(4), 584–599.
- Iqbal, J. (2010). *Primary Data of Sillanwali Handi Crafts*. Retrieved from <http://www.scci.pk/Research/Sillanwali.pdf>
- Ishak, S., & Omar, A. R. C. (2013). Do small firms possess innovative behavior? Evidence from Malaysia. *Journal of Innovation Management in Small & Medium Enterprises*, 2013, 1.
- Jasra, J., Hunjra, A. I., Rehman, A. U., Azam, R. I., & Khan, M. A. (2011). Determinants of business success of small and medium enterprises. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(20).
- Khalique, M., Isa, A. H. B. M., & Nassir Shaari, J. A. (2011). Challenges for Pakistani SMEs in a knowledge-based economy. *Indus Journal of Management & Social Sciences*, 5(2).
- Khan, M. M. (2015). Sources of finance available for SME sector in Pakistan. *International Letters of Social and Humanistic Sciences*, 47, 184–194.
- Khan, S. (2015). Impact of sources of finance on the growth of SMEs: evidence from Pakistan. *Decision*, 42(1), 3–10.
- Khattak, J. K., Arslan, M., & Umair, M. (2011). SMEs' export problems in Pakistan. *E3 Journal of Business Management and Economics*, 2(5), 192–199.
- Khawaja, S. (2006). Unleashing the Potential of the SME Sector with a Focus on Productivity Improvements. *Pakistan Development Forum*, 10–11.
- Kim-Soon, N., Ahmad, A. R., Kiat, C. W., & Sapry, H. R. (2017). SMEs are embracing innovation for business performance. *Journal of Innovation Management in Small & Medium Enterprises*, 1, 1–17.
- Köksal, M. H., & Kettaneh, T. (2011). Export problems experienced by high-and low-performing manufacturing companies. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 23(1), 108.
- Kongolo, M. (2010). Job creation versus job shedding and the role of SMEs in economic development. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(11), 2288–2295.
- Manigart, S., De Waele*, K., Wright, M., Robbie, K., Desbrières, P., Sapienza, H., & Beekman, A. (2000). Venture capitalists, investment appraisal and accounting information: a comparative study of the USA, UK, France, Belgium and Holland. *European Financial Management*, 6(3), 389–403.
- Matamanda, S. H., & Chidoko, C. (2017). Accessing formal financing by Small and Medium Enterprises in Zimbabwe: The case of SMEs and banks in Chiredzi Urban. *Cell*, 263(773), 555908.
- Matlay, H., & Westhead, P. (2005). Virtual teams and the rise of e-entrepreneurship in Europe. *International Small Business Journal*, 23(3), 279–302.
- Maunganidze, F. (2013). The Role of Government in the Establishment and Development of SMEs in Zimbabwe: Virtues and Vices. *Journal of Business Administration and Education*, 4(1), 1–16.
- Modimootsile, K. G. (2005). *Possibilities and constraints to development of small-scale entrepreneurs that cater for the tourism industry in Ngamiland District of Northern Botswana*.

- Porter, M. E., Lopez-Claros, A., Schwab, K., & Sala-I-Martin, X. (2006). *The Global Competitiveness Report 2006-2007: World Economic Forum, Geneva, Switzerland 2006*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Qureshi, J. A. (2012). The Role of Small and Medium-Size Enterprises in Socio-Economic Sustainability in Pakistan. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 12(19).
- Qureshi, J., & Herani, G. M. (2011). The Role of Small and Medium-size Enterprises (SMEs) in the Socio-economic Stability of Karachi. *Indus Journal of Management & Social Science (IJMSS)*, 5(1), 30–44.
- Ramlee, S., & Berma, B. (2013). Financing gap in Malaysian small-medium enterprises: A supply-side perspective. *South African Journal of Economic and Management Sciences*, 16(5), 115–126.
- Rasak, B. (2012). Small and medium scale enterprises (smes): a panacea for economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Management and Corporate Governance*, 4(6), 86–98.
- RAZIQA, A. (2014). Strategic Planning And High Performance Human Resource Management Practices In Pakistani Smes. *Management and Marketing Journal*, 12(2), 123–134.
- Romijn, H., & Albaladejo, M. (2002). Determinants of innovation capability in small electronics and software firms in southeast England. *Research Policy*, 31(7), 1053–1067.
- Saleh, A. S., & Ndubisi, N. O. (2006). An evaluation of SME development in Malaysia. *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 2(1), 1–14.
- Serra, K. L. O., & García, N. B. P. (2013). Factors contributing to product innovation in a value chain: Three case studies. *Journal of Innovation Management in Small & Medium Enterprises*, 2013, 1.
- SMEDA Survey Report. (2009).
- Ul Hassan, M. (2008). Microfinance in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Pakistan: practices and problems in the prevailing system and prospects for Islamic finance. *イスラーム世界研究: Kyoto Bulletin of Islamic Area Studies*, 2(1), 231–237.
- Westhead, P., & Wright, M. (2000). *Advances in entrepreneurship* (Vol. 1). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Zafar, A., & Mustafa, S. (2017). SMEs and its role in economic and socio-economic development of Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 6(4).